

Qualitative Study on Complex Conflicts Resolution in Nigeria: Dynamics, Causes and Effects of Military Civil Wars

Ekuerhare Sylvia Efe¹

efe_sylvia@yahoo.com
[08023282224](tel:08023282224)

¹Directorate of General Studies, Federal University of Petroleum Resources, Effurun, Delta State. Nigeria

Abstract

This article examined the qualitative study on complex conflicts resolution in Nigeria, focusing on the dynamics, causes and effects of military civil wars. It adopts a systematic review method, and several focused on the use of secondary data such as using information from journal articles, books and e-books, database, through the use of various search engines such as google scholar, Google, Research gate, among others, Materials and information of interest cover between 2010 and 2023. In addition, content analysis was used to group materials into major themes, thereby subjecting them to thematic analysis towards addressing the objective of the study. The findings of the study revealed that complex conflict such as the military civil war is fluid in its dynamic and its patterns, processes, and with respect to the factors that shape it and could affect the various aspects of national activities. Several sources of complex conflicts are also identified and include political, economics, religious, structure and type of society, among others. In conclusion, complex conflicts have cumulative disastrous effects on individual, family, social, economic, religion and political activities. The study therefore recommends that there is need for peacekeeping managers and organization to tailor peace-building efforts directly towards the understanding of the dynamics, causes and effects of the conflict.

Keywords: Complex Conflicts, Military civil war, Dynamics of Civil war, Causes of Civil war, Effects of Civil war.

Introduction

Conflict is a common universal issue arising from social interactions and could be in different forms such as interpersonal, inter or intra-groups, organizational, among others (Kumar, 2023). It does not necessarily connote negative phenomenon, because it could be a certain catalyst for change, growth, progress and development (Lamb & Gregg, 2018; Kumar, 2023). However, conflict can escalate or de-escalate, depending on the interactions and responses of the parties or groups involved (Kamar, 2023). Hence, certain type of conflict such as complex conflicts could pose significant concern to growth, progress and development.

Complex conflicts are continuously increasing in the global society, and are emergence of interplay among several factors such as the socioeconomic, political, religion among other factors (Kumar, 2023). According to Lamb and Gregg (2018), there are increasing uncertainties, volatilities, and increasing actors, which are combination of domestic, regional, or international affiliations that increases the complexity of conflicts in a society. Hence, parties supporting conflict could be highly fragmented, deploying several interconnectedness and social networks (which could be at proximity and/or distance), and are also increasingly engaging in several complex competitive alliances characterized by the lack of trust, and power manipulation and sharing (Lamb & Gregg, 2018).

Furthermore, there is an underlying secret selfishness and instability among these increase competitive alliances that could further increase the likelihood of such complex conflict to reoccur, thereby disrupting the peace of the society on a continuous basis. This could lead to the reason for the dynamics of the changing pattern of occurrence of complex conflicts in a society. There are several causes of complex conflicts and could include economic inequality, historical tensions among different parties or groups in a given society, cultural differences, political issues, among others (Lamb & Gregg, 2018). According to the International Committee of the Red Cross (2023), complex conflict has three main characteristics, which are characterized by an increasing number of armed conflicts, driven by the proliferation of non-international armed conflicts, a growing number of actors that are engaged in and responsible for it, and an increased prevalence of support relationships.

Burgess and Burgess (2019) revealed that complex conflicts are seriously destructive and pose several negative threats and effects to our present and future of the society hence could pose negative effect on sustainable development. This is because, it ruins personal lives, prevents society from solving common social, economic, religion and political problems, leading to chaos and increasing and persistent large-scale violence. Normal conflicts could be understood by investigating the systems, but complex conflicts are complex and could be well understood by focusing on the dynamic of systems (Lamb & Gregg, 2018). Systems are characterized by their boundary, which demarcates the endogenous factors (which are major

components of the system) from the exogenous factors (which are separate entities from the system). Hence, ordinary conflicts may be traced to the immediate system, but complex conflicts exist in a dynamic of system (Lamb & Gregg, 2018). These dynamics of the system makes it impossible to be able to handle such conflicts due to the fragmentation of major actors that may not possibly appear in the system.

Hence, the inability to constructively handle such conflict is the most serious, and the most neglected, problem facing humanity that could fragment and distort societal values and destroy development efforts in any society (Burgess & Burgess, 2019). Successfully addressing destructive effects of complex conflicts requires a large-scale effort that could mobilize the full range of human ingenuity from different values, different attitudes, different cultures, different economic concerns, different educational levels, different religions, different cultures (Burgess & Burgess, 2019). Unless there is a concerted effort towards the understanding of the complexity of the conflict system, efforts towards cushioning such complex conflicts may fail to achieve the desired outcome. Applying the Dynamical Systems Theory (DST) by Coleman et al., (2007), which tends to explain the changing patterns of interests, motivations and identities over the cause of time, this article focuses on complex conflicts, by examining the dynamics, causes and effects of military civil wars towards cushioning complex conflicts occurrences.

Addressing complex conflicts, Burgess (2015) noted that they may likely involve long series of often overlapping dispute episodes that focus on addressing different aspects of an overall conflict. From one perspective, such individual disputes could be subjected to negotiation or mediation while other disputes may be subjected to legal or political processes, public demonstrations, or police or military action. At another point, it may include both the former and the later, making it more complex in understanding and handling hence, may need effective conflict analysis or mapping. This conflict analysis and mapping tend to clarify what is going on, particularly in trying to focus on understanding the relationships and conflict dynamics, couple with the static parties, interests, and needs. In addition, there should be constructive responses that focus on the parts of the system and also in relation to other interventions in the system (Burgess, 2015).

Kamar (2023) defines conflict as complex involving several cognitive, emotional, and behavioral factors which cuts across perceptions, attitudes, emotions, communication, and actions. Complex conflicts have been termed to be wicked problems and are much characterized as being highly resistant to resolutions and are socially, economically and politically sophisticated issues to be dealt with (Rapaport & Ireland, 2012). They are also associated with high levels of uncertainty because of the diversity of stakeholders' views, and the interconnection of issues, which often leads them to political standstill instead of leading to political resolution (Rapaport & Ireland, 2012).

Complex conflicts could also be regional and international and could evolve from unrest phenomenon from the socio-economic, political and military stress in the society with several other related issues such as fight for power, territories, and disputes over natural resources, national identity, and religiosity, among others. This could lead to irreversible consequences that could excavate prolonged civil wars which could also encompass high level of armed conflicts, terrorism, human rights violations, ethnic conflicts, social, economic and also political instability (Sørli, Gleditsch & Strand, 2005; Gambari, 2011).

The conflict complexity, most often pose significant adverse effects that tend to be felt beyond the concerned groups or parties of the conflict, because of its gradual, and continuous expansion of the conflict to several other regions, which could eventually, in most times, reach a global dimension hence, it could be unpredictable (Rapaport & Ireland, 2012). Understanding the dynamics, causes and effects of such complex conflict such as military civil wars can help predict and manage the course of the conflict. To this end, this study focuses on complex conflicts, by examining the dynamics, causes and effects of military civil wars towards cushioning complex conflicts occurrences.

Theoretical Underpinning

The article focuses on the adoption of the Dynamical Systems Theory (DST) by Coleman et al. (2007) to explain the complex dynamics, sources and effects of conflicts. According to Horowitz (1985); Lake & Rothchild (1996) and Penu and Osei-Kufuor (2016), the Dynamical Systems Theory could provide an understanding for complex conflicts which address key issues such as security dilemma, fear of extinction, fear of the future, among others. From the perspective of the Dynamical Systems Theory, complex conflicts have an interrelated connection, influencing each other, which could change over time towards creating a complex issue that could pose significant effect on the society at large. Therefore, this study focuses on using the DST to explain the dynamics, causes and effects of military civil wars towards cushioning complex conflicts occurrences in the society at large.

Methodology

The systematic review approach was used in this article to achieve its aims and objectives. Information and materials used were obtained from journal articles, books, and other similar materials, including online materials that address the major aim and objective of this study. In addition, information and materials selected focused on year range between 2010 and 2023 so as to obtain more recent information that meet the aims of the study. Also, the study uses Cochrane reviews style of reviewing literature by Chapman (2014), particularly in the searching process to obtain useful materials that are used in the study. This also follows the use of PICOS (Richardson, 1995) as represented below:

P – Problem or Population

I – Intervention

C – Control or comparator

O – Outcome(s)

S - Study type (e.g. quantitative, qualitative)

Also, search engine used for this systematic review are google, google scholar and other search engines, yielding several results and outcomes but very few (only seven articles) were selected that were fit and used for this study, towards meeting the goal of the study. Moreover, the information and materials were subjected to thematic analysis where they are grouped into various themes of the objectives and content analysis was also used to analyze the information resources obtained towards addressing the objective of the study.

Presentation of Results

The result section focuses on providing responses to understanding of complex conflicts, with focus on explaining the dynamics, causes and effects of military civil wars.

Dynamics of Military Civil Wars

According to Kamar (2023), conflict dynamics connote the patterns, processes, and factors that could shape the course of conflicts and involves many factors such as power imbalances, identity issues, emotions, and communication breakdowns. Penu and Osei-Kufuor (2016) argued that the dynamics of complex conflicts could pose significant implications on the elastic success of peace-building efforts exerted towards the conflicts. This also makes peace-building effort a complex and a continuous evolving issue which is characterized with the understanding of the long-term nature of the peace-building process, understanding the interdependence of the actors involved and also the multidimensional patterns of the peace-building process (African Centre for Constructive Resolution of Disputes, 2013).

However, Lamb and Gregg (2018) affirmed that, putting into consideration the complexity of the system, and the systems theories, it is hypothesized that, when humans and other organisms are in a complex system, they over time adapt. However, bringing into play the Dynamical systems theory (DST) by Coleman et al. (2007), this may not hold in practical term, because of the complex dynamics of the situation, multiple actors, system, among others that evolve over time- this could further complicate the issue. Therefore, it is not a gainsaying to conclude that, understanding the dynamics of complex conflicts that they are fluid and could be influenced by several factors such as political, economics, religious, among others, Coleman (2011) and Kamar (2023), advised that peace-building efforts directed towards solving complex conflicts must be driven and directed towards the heavily reliance on the understanding of the dynamics of the conflict in question and of interest.

Causes of Military Civil Wars

Penu and Osei-Kufuor (2016) specify that there are different sources of complex conflicts (military civil war) and could constitute from multiple sources such as individual, group, communal, regional, and international. Coleman, Vallacher, Nowak, & Bui-Wrzosinska (2007) revealed that it tends to increase over time as these multiple groups interact with each other in a continuous and complex reaction through hostilities. According to Mitchell (2005), sources of such complex conflicts often transform and change continually, which could pose either lower or higher effects on peace-building efforts.

According to Jackson (2003) and Rapaport & Ireland (2012), the structure and type of society may also constitute as major sources of complex conflicts. Structure could evolve and change over time because of the frequent turbulences that could be found within the environment hence, this could be a major source of complex conflicts. Also, the type of system, which could be unitary, pluralist and coercive, could also be a major course of complex conflicts. The unitary sees the society as common purposes and agreed objectives, but society or system that operates the pluralist and coercive relationships could be more conflict driven. This is because, pluralist and coercive system is characterized with very few or no common interests, having conflicting values and beliefs, among others hence, this may drive complex conflicts in such system. Bahnasy (2023) noted that the main causes of civil wars could be demographical, geographical, and environmental; economic and resources; government type and regime change; institutions power; and historical and cultural variables.

In addition, Leenders (2007) noted that, the complexities of conflicts revolve around four transnational networks, which are military, political, economic, and social. Military is the movement of weapons and mercenaries, political consists of political networking and relationships, economic focuses on cross border issues related to the trade of illegal goods and social aspects of such complex conflicts focuses on issues related to occupation, cross border migration and diasporas. Moreover, Leenders (2007) argued that there is an interconnectedness and relationship among these conflicts, which makes it very strong, for such to be overlooked or reduced to single intra-state conflict.

Also, Fajana (2000) cited by Omisore and Abiodun (2014) identifies two major sources of complex conflicts which are the internal and external sources. Also, Omisore and Abiodun (2014) identified that causes of complex conflicts could be goal differences, authority relationships, roles and expectations, jurisdictional ambiguities, among others.

Effects of Complex Conflicts

Aliyev (2019) noted that some civil wars could be more deadly than others; this could be because of several issues as addressed by the dynamics and sources of such complex conflict. Civil war affects the lives of virtually every man, woman, as the entire communities. churches, businesses, homes, barns, tents fields, livestock and homes were looted and destroyed. Makpor and Leite (2017) and Ajodo-Adebanjoko (2017) noted that conflicts, which include complex conflicts could cause significant effect to the community development, leading to disempowerment, changes in the community structures, reduces social involvement, cooperation and activities, affecting the socio-economic status of the community, among others.

It could also destroy the basic necessities such as drinking water, roads, health centres, schools, among others (Makpor and Leite, 2017). Afinotan and Ojatorotu (2019), also revealed that such conflicts could affect several economic activities such as vegetation, SMEs, businesses, farmlands and human settlements, among others. Also, Bahnasy (2023) noted that complex conflicts could pose significant effect on the nation. In addition, Le, Bui and Uddin (2022), revealed that conflicts could have negative short- and long-term endogenous effects on the economic and social variables of development.

Discussion

This article explained the dynamics, causes and effects of military civil wars towards cushioning complex conflicts occurrences in the society. The findings of this article revealed that complex conflict is fluid in its dynamic with respect to the patterns, processes, and the factors that shape it and that because of the complex dynamics of the situation, it tends to involve multiple actors, system, among others that evolve over time, making it to be more complex scenario. Hence, peace-building efforts directed towards solving complex conflicts must be driven and directed towards the heavily reliance on the understanding of the dynamics of the conflict in question and of interest. This concurs with the findings of Lamb and Gregg (2018) that complex conflicts have increasing uncertainties, volatile, and increasing actors, which made it very complex to handle and also increase the tremendous effect it has on the society.

This also justifies the work of Red Cross (2023) that, complex conflict consists of three main features namely an increase number of armed conflicts, it is driven by the increasing non-international armed conflicts, and also an increasing number of actors, couple with an increased prevalence of support relationships, connoting the extent on it dynamics. In addition, apart from the political, economics, religious, among others sources of complex conflicts, the structure and type of society are also of paramount. Moreover, the effect of complex conflicts could cut across social activities, economic activities, political activities, religious activities, among others. This concurs with the findings of Sørli et al. (2005) and Gambari (2011) that complex conflicts have certain undertone sources such as social, economic, political, religion, among others. This supports the work of Burgess and Burgess (2019) that complex conflicts are seriously destructive and could pose several negative destructive effects to both the present and future of the society thereby negatively effecting sustainable development. This also supports the work of Lamb & Gregg (2018) that complex conflicts affect and ruins personal lives, prevents society from solving common social, economic, religion and political problems, leading to chaos, increasing and persistent large-scale violence.

Conclusion

This article explained the dynamics, causes and effects of military civil wars towards cushioning complex conflicts occurrences in the society. In conclusion, it was revealed that complex conflict such as the military civil war is fluid in its dynamic patterns, processes, and the with respect to the factors that shape it. Several sources of complex conflicts are also

identified and include political, economics, religious, structure and type of society, among others. In addition, complex conflicts have cumulative disastrous effects on individual, family, social, economic, religion and political activities.

Recommendations

The study therefore recommends that:

1. There is need for peacekeeping managers and organization to tailor peace-building efforts directly towards the understanding of the dynamics, causes and effects of the conflict,
2. There should also be the need for educative strategies to make people aware of the disastrous and devastating effects of such complex conflicts, thereby advising them to shorn every political and religious individual that may want to use such avenue to lure them into such conflicts.
3. peacekeeping managers and organization who are also involved in peace building should also put into consideration the several actors that are causing or involved in such complex conflicts towards making a better inform decision to curb such conflicts in the society.

References

- Afinotan, L.A., & Ojajorotu, V., (2019). The Niger Delta crisis: Issues, challenges and prospects. *African Journal of Political Science and International Relations*, 3 (5), 191-198. <https://gisf.ngo/wp-content/uploads/2014/09/0070-Afinotan-Ojajorotu-2009-Niger-Delta.pdf>
- African Centre for Constructive Resolution of Disputes, (2013). *ACCORD Peace-building Handbook* (1st ed.). African Centre for Constructive Resolution of Disputes
- Ajodo-Adebanjoko, A., (2017). Towards ending conflict and insecurity in the Niger Delta region, A collective non-violent approach. *ACCORD*, <https://reliefweb.int/report/nigeria/towards-ending-conflict-and-insecurity-niger-delta-region>
- Aliyev, H., (2019). Why Are Some Civil Wars More Lethal Than Others? The Effect of Pro-Regime Proxies on Conflict Lethality, *Political studies*. 68 (3). <https://doi.org/10.1177/0032321719862752>
- Bahnasy, A., (2024). The Consequences of Civil-Military Relations on Civil Wars in the Middle East [Master's Thesis, the American University in Cairo]. AUC Knowledge Fountain. <https://fount.aucegypt.edu/etds/2195>
- Burgess, H. (2015). Complexity: Sources of Complexity, The Beyond Intractability Project. <https://www.beyondintractability.org/essay/complexity>
- Burgess, H. & Burgess, G. (2019). The Intractable Conflict Challenge, The Beyond Intractability Project. <https://www.beyondintractability.org/frontiers/intractable-conflict-challenge>
- Coleman, P. T., Vallacher, R., Nowak, A., and Bui-Wrzosinska, L. (2007) "Intractable Conflict as an Attractor: Presenting a Dynamical Model of Conflict, Escalation, and Intractability." *American Behavioral Scientist*, 50(11), pp. 1454–147
- Coleman, P.T., (2011). *The Five Percent: Finding Solutions to Seemingly Impossible Conflicts*. Perseus Books
- Gambari I., (2011). Multilateralism: Challenges of International Mediation in Regional Conflicts. *African Conflict & Peacebuilding Review*, 1(1), 134. Indiana University Press
- Horowitz, D. T. (1985). *Ethnic groups in conflict*. Berkeley, CA: University of California Press.
- International Committee of the Red Cross, (2023). Complex conflict characteristics, Support Relationships in Armed Conflict, <https://sri.icrc.org/risks-opportunities/complex-conflicts/complex-conflict-characteristics>
- Jackson, M., (2003), *Systems Thinking - Creative Holism for Managers*. John Wiley and Sons, Chichester, UK, 19;
- Kumar, M., (2023). Conflict Resolution in Complex Situations, Tutorials point. <https://www.tutorialspoint.com/conflict-resolution-in-complex-situations>
- Lake, D. A., & Rothchild, D. (1996). Ethnic Fears and Global Engagement: The International Spread and Management of Ethnic Conflict. *Working Paper*, Institute on Global Conflict and Cooperation
- Lamb, R.D. & Gregg, M.R. (2018), Complex Systems and Conflict, Strategic Studies Institute, US Army War College, <https://www.jstor.org/stable/pdf/resrep20101.7.pdf>
- Le, T-H., Bui, M-T., & Uddin, G.S., (2022). Economic and social impacts of conflict: A cross-country analysis. *Economic Modelling*, 115, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.econmod.2022.105980>
- Leenders, R., (2007). Regional Conflict Formations: is the Middle East next?, *Third World Quarterly*, 28(5), 961
- Makpor, M.E., & Leite, R., (2017). The Nigerian Oil Industry: Assessing Community Development and Sustainability. *International Journal of Business and Management*, 12 (7), 58-69

- Mitchell, C. R. (2005). *Conflict, Social Change, and Conflict Resolution: An Enquiry*. Berlin: Berghof Research Center for Constructive Conflict Management. www.berghof-handbook.net
- Omisore, B.O., & Abiodun, A.R., (2014). Organizational Conflicts: Causes, Effects and Remedies. *International Journal of Academic Research in Economics and Management Sciences*, 3(6), 118-137. DOI: 10.6007/IJAREMS/v3-i6/1351.
- Penu, D.A.C.P., & Osei-Kufuor, P., (2016). Understanding Conflict Dynamics: Identifying ‘attractors’ in the Alavanyo - Nkonya Conflict, *Research on Humanities and Social Sciences*, 6(8), 90-98
- Rapaport, B., & Ireland, V. (2012). Understanding the Dynamics of System-of-Systems in Complex Regional Conflicts. *Procedia Computer Science*, 12, 43–48. doi:10.1016/j.procs.2012.09.027
- International Committee of the Red Cross, (2023). Complex conflict characteristics <https://sri.icrc.org/risks-opportunities/complex-conflicts/complex-conflict-characteristics>
- Richardson, W.S., (1995). "The well-built clinical question: a key to evidence based-decisions". *APC Journal Club*. 123, 3: A12–A13.
- Sørli, M.E., Gleditsch, N.P. & Strand, H. (2005), Why is There So Much Conflict in the Middle East?, *The Journal of Conflict Resolution*, 49(1), 141-16